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OPEN UNIVERSITY**

Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management

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**Remediation Study to use Dolomite to Neutralize Sulfuric Acid in the Abandoned
Copper Mine Pits in Marinduque**

Faculty of Management and Development Studies

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Acceptance Page

This Special Project entitled: "REMEDICATION STUDY TO USE DOLOMITE TO NEUTRALIZE SULFURIC ACID IN THE ABANDONED COPPER MINE PITS IN MARINDUQUE" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies; U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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Biographical Sketch

Fernando S. Guevara is currently the President of Guevara and Partners Inc., a private corporation that is engaged in engineering consultancy and environmental studies for 30 years. He finished his Bachelor in Science - Mechanical Engineering in Adamson University. He is a Professional Mechanical Engineer in the Philippines and a Professional Engineer in Minnesota and California in the United States of America.

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ABSTRACT

FERNANDO S. GUEVARA Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management. Faculty of Management and Development Studies. University of the Philippines Open University. May 23, 2022. “**A Remediation Study to use Dolomite to Neutralize Sulfuric Acid in the Abandoned Copper Mine Pits in Marinduque**”.

Special Problem Adviser: Prof. Consuelo Habito, PhD

BACKGROUND PROBLEM

Marcopper started producing copper, gold and silver from the *Tapian* pit from 1969 to 1991. The tailings were sent to the San Antonio impoundment pit until 1975. It shifted its tailing disposal to the *Calanacan* Bay in 1976. One hundred twenty (120) million tons of copper mine tailings has been discharged in the *Calanacan* Bay (USGS, 2000). It is estimated that the tailing discharge of Marcopper was 200 to 300 million tons between 1975 to 1990 (USGS, 2000). In 1991 after finding that the San Antonio impoundment pit contains copper and other minerals the mining activity shifted to the San Antonio impoundment pit and with the approval of the Philippine government agency , the “*Kagawaran ng Kapaligiran at Likas Yaman*” (KKLY), discharged mine tailings from Calanacan Bay to the abandoned *Tapian* pit. The dewatering tunnel, that is used to drain water at the *Tapian* pit located 195 meter above the Makalunpit river, was plugged to prevent the mine tailings from contaminating *Boac* and *Mogpog* rivers. This means *Boac* river and *Mogpog* river_ thru Makalumpit river has been exposed to acid mine drainage (AMD) since 1969. On March 24, 1996 Marcopper cease mining operation when “the plug

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in the 195-m level drainage adit failed catastrophically. The plug failure resulted in the release of an estimated 1.5-3 million cubic meters (UNEP, 1996) of sulfuric tailings (AMD) slurry from the Tapian Pit storage area into the *Makalumpit* river, *Mogpog*, *Boac* river, and eventually the ocean west of the island” (USGS, 2000). After the disaster, *Placer Dome*, disposed its financial ownership in Marcopper and created the *Placer Dome* Technical Services (PDTS) to determine options to remediate the major environment mining disaster. One of the immediate measures was to create a one-kilometer berm on both sides of the Boac riverbanks to protect the farmlands from over flooding. PDTS also dredge the Boac river 20 meters deep. PDST re-plugged the 195-meter adit to prevent the discharge of AMD into the *Makalumpit*, *Mogpog* and *Boac* rivers. One proposal of PDTS was to provide a submarine pipeline towards the sea where the mine AMD tailings will be dropped into the depths of the ocean in Tablas Strait. This proposal was denied by the “*Kagawaran ng Kapaligiran at Likas Yaman*” (KKLY).

A study made by the “*Joint U.S. Geological Survey – Armed Forces Institute of Pathology Reconnaissance Field Evaluation, on May 12-19, 2000 by Geoffrey S. Plumlee, Robert A. Morton, Terence P. Boyle, Jack H. Medlin, and Jose A. Centeno*” on the “An Overview of Mining-Related Environmental and Human Health Issues, Marinduque Island, Philippines” in collaboration with the Office of the Governor of Marinduque concluded that “*the potential magnitude and impacts of all these problems are so great that we strongly recommend the implementation of a general mining-environmental*

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assessment and monitoring program on the island. The primary goals of such a monitoring and assessment program should be to (1) understand and define the magnitude of the different mining-environmental problems, (2) prioritize the problems for remediation, and (3) look for creative, cost-effective ways to help mitigate or remediate the problems”.

This study has its purpose inspired by item (3) recommendation.

Keywords: remediation, acid mine drain, water vitro assaying, reverse osmosis

Hervando Quiñe

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I would like to show my appreciation to Prof. Consuelo Habito, PhD, for his guidance in my research and for helping me overcome difficulties in coping with the university's academic procedures. I would also like to thank the previous professors from the Faculty of Management and Development Studies who instilled the foundation for this course. that provided insights on the study.

Finally, I would like to thank my family and friends who provided encouragement throughout the course of the research.

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DEDICATED TO:

This research is dedicated to the people of Marinduque who have suffered from this mining activity that resulted in a major environmental disaster. It is hoped that this study would contribute to the knowledge on the rehabilitation or remediation of abandoned mine pits in the country. Lastly, this is for people and organizations who are part of environmental movements of different advocacies who are nameless and faceless heroes and agents of change.

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Abstract

The remediation¹ study is about determining the viability of using dolomite as a neutralizing agent to acid mine drain or AMD. This study used qualitative and quantitative methods in evaluating the approved South Korea Publication of KR100847444B1 on Dolomite and Case laboratory test study of dolomite in *South Africa's West Rand Gold Field* together with a comparative assaying findings of the *United States Geological Survey* (USGS) team and the Porcopper (Romania) data on metallic elements to expand an affirmative conclusion. Marcopper mine tailing has unique situation where two mine pit Tapian and San Antonio are located up in the mountains of Marinduque seated in rocks with low ANC² and low NAG-ph³ producing acid and two tunnels Adit 310 and Adit 195 located at the base of the pit (Shown in Picture 1.0). These tunnels are under high head pressure from AMD impounded in these pits and unfortunately finds its way to the Boac and Mogpog river thru these tunnels whose protective walls collapse. This study concluded that Dolomite found to be available in the Philippines, is advantageous economically and can effectively react with sulfuric acid to produce neutral chemical product that is not harmful to the river. The method would entail draining the AMD in the mine pits using chemical pumps and neutralize it using the reverse osmosis process. The product of this process will produce non-potable water source for the community. When the pit is emptied with AMD, dolomite will refill the empty mine pits up to 3/4 of the depth of the pits to neutralize the remaining sulfuric acid produced by the pit walls. The exposed

¹ Remediation means removal of environmental contaminants

² ANC means Acid Neutralizing Capacity is a measure of the ability water to neutralize acid inputs

³ NAG-ph means Net Acid Generation-ph Test that results to less than 4.5 ph value is acid generating

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pyrite walls that still contains sulfide iron minerals will continue to produce sulfuric acid. These walls will be mitigated by cementing the walls and providing trench drains that will collect and process AMD thru reverse osmosis. However, any element of lead and arsenic are resolve after separate study on the reaction of these metals to human blood.

Picture 1.0 Marcopper Environmental Geology

Purpose:

The purpose of this study is to confirm the use dolomite as the main neutralizing agent to replace present mine tailing liquid waste. The mine tailings is an acid mine drain (AMD) of sulfuric acid that was a result of sulfide iron minerals exposure or mixture with air and water. The AMD leaks to the *Boac* and *Mogpog* river (even at present) because of the high

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head pressure exerted by the mine tailings to Adit 195 in the Tapian mine pit and Adit 315 in San Antonio mining pit. The AMD in the mine pit will be pumped out and process thru reverse osmosis method. Once the AMD are removed dolomite will be filled into the pit up to 3/4 of the depth of the pit. Rehabilitation of acid soil and rocks thru liming, bio-inoculation and right choice of plant species will be treated as a separate study and not covered by this purpose.

Methodology:

To achieve the purpose of this qualitative study a content analysis of documents will be mainly use as a means getting quantitative relevant information. The South Korea Publication of KR100847444B1 July 21, 2008 titled *Method for Neutralizing Sulfuric Acid Wastewater by Using Calcined Dolomite* will be reviewed. And, a test study of dolomite in *South Africa's West Rand Gold Field* will demonstrate how important dolomite is in protecting underground water resource. These reviews and evaluations will confirm and validate that by using dolomite, AMD leaks to rivers and streams will be minimized or totally eliminated. The study will confirm the AMD assaying data of Procopper in Valea Sesie in Romania last 2017 [1] vis-a-vis with the river water assay data of the *United States Geological Survey (USG)* in 2000. The *USG* has more detail test of the mine tailings metal elements in relation to human blood samples. While Porcopper conducted a scientific AMD assaying of metal elements, the *USGS* has a more complete array of elements concentration measured of the Boac and Mogpog river.

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1.0 Introduction:

Marcopper has considerable size of porphyry copper mineral ore production in the Philippines that process less than 1% copper ore concentrates. Being a scattered porphyry-type of copper mineral ore, extracting the ore used an open pit method. Unfortunately, the open pit sits in a low acid neutralizing with a high generating acid rock formation. Consequently, open pit will disturb large amount of mineral capacity rocks formation which is largely pyrite or ferrous sulfide rocks that when exposed reacts with oxygen thru air and rainwater will continuously produce large quantity of sulfuric acid unless the process is mitigated. In the case of Marcopper it open two mine pit located in the Tapian and San Antonio mountains. The mine tailing of the *Tapian* pit is drained indirectly thru the San Antonio tail ponds to the *Calanacan* Bay in *Sta. Cruz, Marinduque*. When the copper ore in the *Tapian* pit was depleted the mining company Marcopper found another source of copper ore beneath the *San Antonio* tailings pond. To extract the copper ore in the *San Antonio* tailing pond the company build a tailings dam along the *Mogpog* River. Prior to this is residents of *Calanacan* Bay complained to the Philippine Government that the 200 million mine tailings that flowed made them sick and deprive them of their livelihood. However, the *Mogpog* mine tailing dam collapsed and damage the *Mogpog* river and flooded the town of *Mogpog*. The government agency “*Kagawaran ng Kapaligiran at Likas Yaman*” (*KKLY*) decided to approve the diversion of the *San Antonio* mining waste to the *Tapian* pit. A tunnel on both *San Antonio* pit and *Tapian* pit named as Adit 310 and Adit 195 respectively was constructed to drain the mine tailing waste to the *Mogpog* dam and the *Boac* river. Unfortunately, the Adit 195 tunnel containment walls collapsed due to

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extremely high head pressure exerted by the mine tailing waste causing the spill of the mine tailings flow into the *Boac* river. Refer to Picture 2.0 below.

Picture 2.0 Marcopper *Tapian* Mining Pit Schematic Section

2.0 Acid Mining Drain

2.1 Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) Chemistry

AMD when discharged to streams and rivers impacts its environment through oxygen depletion, release of heavy metals, and acidity of ferric ion (Fe^{3+}) precipitation as a result of metal mining activities (See Table 1 and Figures 1, 2, 3, 4, 5c).

Figure 1.3 Tapian ore-body (open pit) in Marinduque in 2002
(Photo: Catherine Coumans/Mining Watch Canada)

Picture 3.0 Acid Mine Drain & Ferrous Sulfide Rocks

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Copper mineral ore deposits contain sulfides that are mined produce acid mine drainage (AMD). Pyrite has its mineral chemical name iron disulfide (FeS_2) (Picture 3.0). FeS_2 containing sulfides are segregated as waste rock of copper mines extraction process. As pyrites combined with water and oxygen it oxidizes to form sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4).⁴

As shown in chemical equations 2 and 3, the different oxidation and reduction reactions of pyrite resulted to AMD [*Oxidation happens when electrons are released from a reactant during a chemical reaction with acid. Reduction happens when electrons are absorbed by a reactant during a chemical reaction with acid.*⁵] This resulted after AMD turns more acidic in a continuous flow of ferrous pyrite from the existing open pit mine.

AMD happen and accumulate in abandoned mines where pyrite rock are left exposed in air and water. The red color in the rivers with AMD are discolorations on the rocks in the form ferrous hydroxide ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$) shown in Equation 3 and 4 which happens almost simultaneously. The color orange water and discoloration on rocks are indication of AMD. The color orange is caused by ferric hydroxide ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$) precipitating out of the water. AMD is neutralized when precipitates are formed. Low pH values, indicate metal ions

⁴ www.cotf.edu

⁵ (www.thoughtco.com)

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remain dissolved as liquid at low pH value indicating high acidity. Iron oxidizes and cause the pH value rises. The color orange change is damaging to marine life since it reduces the quantity of solar radiation that can be absorbed by water, negatively influencing the photosynthesis process and impairs the vision for animals living underwater. As the sediments settle-down, it covers the river bottom and stifling the food supply of river-bottom-creatures.

Equation 4 shows that exposure to hydrogen ions of mine rocks in water (H₂O), AMD (sulfuric acid) affects the acidity of a river stream. The amount of acid in a solution is a standard is measure of acidity in pH values. For AMD it is not a good measurement of acidity due to clustering of hydrogen ions (H⁺). In determining the concentration of AMD, it must show the quantity of hydrogen ions left in the buffered⁶ mixture of the river. For instance, measuring pH values cannot high concentration of AMD in a river due to high amount of alkaline disoluted carbonates. Measuring the amount of hydrogen ions over basic ions as "total acidity," is a reasonable quantification of acid mine drainage. Example amount in ppm to pH value (Table 4 and Table 5 below).

AMD reduces the "buffering capacity of water" without significantly changing the pH value of water due to the separation and formation of insoluable carbonate and bicarbonate ions that at the same time produce small amount of carbonic acid (H₂CO₃).

⁶ Buffer solution is at its saturated point that it can no longer change the pH value even by adding more acid solution.

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Further exposure of carbonate to AMD, the soluble mixture will at below 4.2 pH value, would be not able to control changes in pH value. At this point all carbonate and bicarbonate ions are exposed to low pH value AMD which is converted to environment and human friendly carbonic acid⁷.

However, carbonic acid can easily reduced into H₂O and CO₂.

2.2 Acid Mining Drain (AMD) Assaying

The absence of known formal assaying data of AMD on the San Antonio Pit and the Tapian Pit, this study decided to refer to an assaying conducted Valea Sesei copper mine tailing impoundment (AMD) in Romania. It is a very relevant investigation conducted by *Piotr Rzymyski et al*⁸ in an study conducted July 25, 2017.

The significance and relevance of this study is the Valea Sesei copper ore is porphyry based like the Tapian and San Antonio mining site. Both sites used the open pit method with similarly less than 1% recovery of copper ore concentrates. This means there is a large volume of pyrite rocks disturbed and reacted to oxygen producing sulfuric acid. "PorCopper (Romania) mining generates large quantities of waste, tailings, and acid outflows causing long-term environmental impacts and potential threats to human

⁷ Carbonic Acid are used to artificially sparkle soft drinks and wines.

⁸ Reference 1

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health”.⁹ In a similar manner the valley of Valea Sesei was flooded with copper mining waste just like the Mogpog and Boac river now covered with mine tailing waste. This study [Rzymiski et al 2017] intends to supplement the absence of any assaying conducted in the Tapian and San Antonio mine tailing waste. I can say that the chemical elements of the Porcopper (Romania) mining waste would be like the Marcopper (Philippines) copper concentrate tailings.

The Valea Sesei investigation is performed to determine the concentration of 65 unprocessed chemicals and cyanide in wastewater from mine tailing pond (AMD) and evaluate the harmfulness of these water samples thru vitro bioassays¹⁰. It concluded that the waters taken from the rivers were extremely acidic (pH 2.1–4.9) and had exceptionally elevated electrical conductivity (280–1561 mS cm⁻¹). However, cyanides were noticeably absent in any sample due the absence cyanide in the flotation process. Instead, high amounts of alkali metals, rare earth elements, and other metal groups was detected. In other sites, the unprocessed chemicals were not high enough to pose a relevant risk.

Fig. 1 Acid mine drainage inflowing from the Rosia Poieni copper mine to Valea Sesei (a) and views of different parts of tailing impoundment (b-e)

⁹ Ibid 8

¹⁰ **Vitro bioassays** are promising tools for the assessment of drinking water quality. The technique is based on living cells that show a response once exposed to toxicants. [www.sciencedirect.com]

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Figure 5c. Confluence of the Paadjao River (left) with the Mogpog River (right), looking downstream. Photo by Mark Logsdon, reproduced from Futures (2004).

Picture 4.0 Colors of the Rivers

Take note of the color of the river waters (Picture 4.0). The red brownish (orange) color shows the river contains ferrous hydroxide ($\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$) that precipitates out of the water to stain the edges of the river are signs of acid mine drainage or AMD. The green color resulted from the remaining acid neutralization process after the attempts to neutralize the AMD with sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), sodium (Na^+), and calcium (Ca^{2+}) ions by adding strong bases, such as caustic soda (NaOH , sodium hydroxide), soda ash (Na_2CO_3 , sodium carbonate), or lime (CaO , calcium oxide, or $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, calcium dihydroxide).

Picture 5.0 Boac River

Picture 6.0 Mogpog River

Picture 7.0 Boac River

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The pictures shown above (Pictures 5.0, 6.0, and 7.0) the similarity between ProCopper in Romania and Marcopper in the Philippines mining tragedy. The data available to characterize chemical composition of the AMD and ARD (acid rock drain) at the ore pit is to evaluate the data taken from ProCopper thru AMD Assaying. While the data taken from Marcopper river are based on Water Vitro Bioassay. I would recommend to conduct AMD Assaying at the Tapian and San Antonio pit ore.

2.3 Water Vitro Bioassay

The high concentration of vitro toxic effects of the valley of Valea Sesei was induced by AMD similarly in the Calanacan Bay, Mogpog and Boac river. Findings in the study (Ryzmski et al July 25, 2017), “showed that blood alterations included redox imbalance in human neutrophils¹¹ followed by lipid peroxidation”¹² and “decreased cell survival, significant aggregation of red blood cells, and increased prothrombin time”. (This medical term means that the water has cancerous potency to effect human blood chemistry) The study highlighted that Valea Şesei contains a large volume of harmful elements, causing health and environmental danger, that requires action to stop the release of chemicals and to start remediation of the area. A similar urgency requires the mitigation of the AMD in the Mogpog and Boac river.

¹¹ **Neutrophils** are a type of white blood cell that helps heal damaged tissues and resolve infections. www.cancer.gov d

¹² **Lipid peroxidation** is an autoxidation process initiated by the attack of free radicals (e.g. OH·, O₂·⁻ and H₂O₂) on phospholipids or PUFA of the membranes of polyunsaturated lipid

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Plumlee et al¹³ (May 9-10, 2000) reviewed preliminary environmental health studies on the Mogpog and Boac rivers that had been conducted by the Kagawaran Nang Kalusugan (KNK) and the Pamantasan Nang Pilipinas Kagawaran nang Toksikolohiya (PNPKND). The test agreements and point of reference for these socio-environmental and health studies were not available to the USGS team. Based on Dr. Centeno's conclusion of the presented scientific facts and statistical analysis, it observed and noted of the, "lack of focus, poor design methodology (e.g., the studies were based on a very small number of subjects), lack of subject assurances and lack of proper controls which are usually included in environmental health studies"¹⁴. However, the PNPKNK studies suggested metal "chelation" therapies [*Chelation therapy is a medical care protocol that remove metals from the body to prevent a person from getting sick*] to the people living in the Calanacan Bay, Mogpog and Boac rivers. Such suggestion indicates that DOH-UPTD finds metal contamination on humans. In the absence of detail comprehensive study of AMD vitro bioassay for the Calanacan Bay, Mogpog and Boac rivers we may consider Valea Sesei AMD vitro bioassay results are similar to the Tapian and San Antonio AMD. In 2011 Mogpog Municipal Health Officer Dr. Edsel Muhi, an epidemiologist, in his report under the Kagawaran ng Kalusugan in Sta. Cruz, residents in Mogpog, Boac, and Sta. Cruz indicated an "elevated arsenic and lead contents in their blood". Dr. Centeno performed blood test on subjects and contends "that lead (Pb) amounts below 25 mg/dL but might cause nutritional deficiencies especially to chelated (contaminated with metal substances) patients".

¹³ Reference [3]

¹⁴ Ibid 13

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2.4 AMD Chemical Elements

Marcopper makes large quantity of tailings, which are the substances of the ore that remains after copper is extracted from the copper ore rocks. It contains high levels of toxic metals shown in Table 1. Aside from the tailings, discharges from mines includes AMD, that helps to further chemical reactions with mineral metals of dissolved pyrite rocks exposed to water resulting to oxidation of iron sulfide producing extremely low pH value chemicals. Valea Sesei Porcopper metal elements are shown in Table 2 and Table 3¹⁵. Picture 8 shows the Tapian and San Antonio mine pit lake.

Figure 5. A. View looking northeast of the north end of the Tapian pit lake. Remnants of the tailings stored in the lake are visible in the central portion of the figure. A panoramic view of the Tapian pit looking southeast is shown on the cover of this report. B. The San Antonio pit lake, looking northwest.

Picture 8.0 Taipan and San Antonio mine Pit Lake

¹⁵ Ibid 9

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Picture 9.0 Boac River and the Sea During the Disaster

Table 1 were taken from the study conducted by Plumlee¹⁶ et al where the water samples taken from different area source affected by the mine spill in Marinduque.

The water samples were subjected to chemical analyses to make a comparative data between a water sample taken from the Boac and Mogpog river and the water sample take from Copper Mine Tailings Impounded in the Valley of the Apuseni Mountains in Romania.

¹⁶ Ibid 15

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Table 1.0 The Chemistry and Toxicity of Discharged Waters Taken from the Boac and Mogpog Rivers of Marinduque Island [3] Reference (page 21)

	Mogpog river	Boac river		Boac domestic well		Boac tailings-tap water leach	Boac tailings-sea water leach	Calancan tailings pore water	“Average” sea water
	(filtered)	(filtered)	(unfiltered)	(filtered)	(unfiltered)	(filtered)	(filtered)	(filtered)	
pH	4.5	8.3		8		3.72	3.08	7.6	7.6 - 8.2
Conductivity uS/cm	1000	800		200		1610	45000	>20000	35000-48000
Cl ppm	4.4	4.4		7.6		29	19000	19000	19353
F ppm	1.1	0.5		02		2.9	2.8	2.1	1.3
NO3 ppm	0.3	<.08		0.8		4.1	<7.0	<7.0	
SO4 ppm	510	320		130		2200	5000	2600	2715
Ag ppb	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	1	4	0.002
Al ppb	7800	33	140	11	690	110000	210000	29	1
As ppb	<0.2	0.3	0.5	1	2	1	30	44	3.7
Ba ppb	39	22	24	8.8	7.9	0.2	4	40	20
Ca ppm	120	100	100	100	100	590	1100	380	415
Cd ppb	11	1	1.1	<0.02	<0.02	14	30	3	0.1
Ce ppb	68	0.3	0.64	<0.01	0.5	42	76	<0.1	0.001
Co ppb	180	17	18	<0.02	0.3	730	730	<0.2	0.003
Cr ppb	<1	<1	<1	<1	1	6	<100	<10	0.3
Cu ppb	22000	100	300	3	7	53000	62000	60	0.1
Fe ppb	4400	76	170	130	1100	620	4800	1000	0.055
K ppb	3500	2700	2600	4600	4600	4800	410000	440000	399000
Li ppb	11	3.2	3.1	3.4	3.7	92	270	140	180
Mg ppm	59	50	50	19	19	170	1600	1300	1280
Mn ppb	7700	1500	1500	150	160	13000	12000	49	0.01 - 0.1
Mo ppb	0.57	18	18	2.1	1.9	0.3	5	81	11
Na ppm	14	12	12	22	23	120	11000	11000	10781
Ni ppb	69	6.4	6.7	<0.1	<0.1	440	460	<1	0.48
P ppb	5	8	10	53	64	19	500	90	60
Pb ppb	2.5	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.51	0.08	<5	0.6	0.001
Rb ppb	3.2	1.8	1.8	1.4	1.7	4.2	20	120	124
Sb ppb	<0.02	<0.02	<0.02	<0.02	<0.02	<0.02	<2	0.5	0.2
Se ppb	<0.2	1	2	<0.2	<0.2	2	100	150	0.17
SiO2 ppm	63	35	35	37	41	83	<50	6	
Sr ppb	570	380	390	440	450	580	7100	7300	7800
U ppb	0.63	0.05	0.05	0.09	0.1	2	4	2.2	3.2
V ppb	0.1	1	1	0.1	3	1	<10	<1	2.5
Zn ppb	1000	27	42	30	35	2300	2300	50	0.39

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Table 2.0 and Table 3.0 below are data were taken from Rzymiski ¹⁷ et al July 25, 2017 titled “The Chemistry and Toxicity of Discharged Waters from Copper Mine Tailings Impounded in the Valley of the Apuseni Mountains in Romania“. The purpose of these tabulated data is to get a comparatively similar chemistry of the water sample taken from Boac and Mogpog river that was contaminated by the impounded copper mine tailings in Marcopper Mines located in Marinduque Island.

Table 2.0 The Chemistry and Toxicity of Discharged Waters from Copper Mine Tailings Impounded in the Valley of the Apuseni Mountains in Romania.[1] Reference (page 21453)

	AMD	WW-1	WW-2	WW-3
Transition metals				
Cd	1.08 ± 0.18 ^a (1.20)	0.22 ± 0.01 ^b (0.24)	<DL	0.01 ± 0.002 ^c (0.0167)
Co	2.20 ± 0.35 ^a (2.47)	0.88 ± 0.07 ^b (0.96)	<DL	0.003 ± 0.006 ^c (0.004)
Cr	0.02 ± 0.02 (0.04)	<DL	<DL	<DL
Cu	259.3 ± 52.4 ^a (291.1)	86.4 ± 6.4 ^b (93.0)	<DL	2.77 ± 0.22 ^c (2.95)
Fe	4669.6 ± 727.9 ^a (5118.2)	410.9 ± 46.7 ^b (459.1)	0.23 ± 0.41 ^c (0.71)	0.006 ± 0.01 ^c (0.01)
Mn	62.3 ± 11.4 ^a (69.8)	25.2 ± 1.8 ^b (26.9)	2.45 ± 0.74 ^c (3.28)	3.82 ± 0.31 ^c (4.09)
Mo	0.01 ± 0.007 ^a (0.015)	0.002 ± 0.003 ^a (0.006)	0.005 ± 0.005 ^a (0.01)	0.02 ± 0.003 ^a (0.025)
Ni	1.48 ± 0.26 ^a (1.65)	0.36 ± 0.03 ^b (0.39)	<DL	0.03 ± 0.007 ^c (0.035)
Ti	0.03 ± 0.03 (0.200)	<DL	<DL	<DL
V	0.508 ± 0.165 ^a (0.606)	<DL	0.001 ± 0.001 ^b (0.003)	<DL
W	0.711 ± 0.228 (0.902)	<DL	<DL	<DL
Zn	610.9 ± 129.9 ^a (692.7)	65.6 ± 7.8 ^b (74.2)	0.04 ± 0.02 ^d (0.06)	4.89 ± 0.35 ^c (5.14)
Zr	0.03 ± 0.03 (0.06)	<DL	<DL	<DL
Post-transition metals				
Al	4488.3 ± 831.1 ^a (5014.8)	826.1 ± 68.1 ^b (894.4)	0.19 ± 0.17 ^d (0.34)	8.94 ± 0.14 ^c (9.10)
Bi	0.61 ± 0.10 ^a (0.71)	0.07 ± 0.08 ^b (0.18)	0.14 ± 0.03 ^b (0.17)	0.07 ± 0.03 ^b (0.10)
In	0.50 ± 0.11 ^a (0.62)	0.26 ± 0.05 ^b (0.32)	0.35 ± 0.04 ^{ab} (0.40)	0.34 ± 0.05 ^{ab} (0.39)
Tl	0.09 ± 0.09 ^a (0.20)	<DL	0.01 ± 0.02 ^a (0.04)	0.03 ± 0.06 ^a (0.11)

	AMD	WW-1	WW-2	WW-3
As	0.107 ± 0.05 (0.153)	<DL	<DL	<DL
B	6.63 ± 1.38 ^a (7.50)	0.54 ± 0.07 ^b (0.63)	0.05 ± 0.07 ^b (0.06)	0.03 ± 0.02 ^b (0.04)
Si	85.7 ± 14.9 ^a (95.2)	28.1 ± 2.1 ^b (30.2)	1.30 ± 0.07 ^c (1.36)	4.70 ± 0.4 ^c (5.0)
Te	0.51 ± 0.25 (0.75)	<DL	<DL	<DL

Table 3 Metalloids in Water Sample Collected At Valea Sesei

¹⁷ Ibid 15

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2.5 Discussion and Conclusion for Marcopper and Porcopper Metal Elements Concentration Data Analysis

Comparing the concentration of the mine tailing AMD and water elements of Marcopper (Philippines) to Porcopper (Romania) (See Table 4) would provide base information on the state of mine elements that are contained in the Tapian and San Antonio mining pit. One similarity in the studies is the absence of cyanide (CN⁻) element. This means cyanide was not used in copper recovery process at the Porcopper and Marcopper. Arsenic (As) is found in the Valea Sesei at 0.153 mg/liter while in Calacan Bay is recorded at 30 ppb (0.030 mg/liter).

The data between Table 1.0 and Tables 2.0 and 3.0 would show that the values of Porcopper mine tailings impounding area are very much higher than the water taken from Boac and Mopog rivers. We may conclude that the suggestion to get water samples at the Tapian and San Antonio mining pit is apparently needed.

Lead (Pb) is found in Marcopper at <0.005 mg/L but none is recorded at the Porcopper mining pits. This confirms Dr. Edsel Muhi metal “chelation” proposal to the the towns of Sta. Cruz, Mogpog and Boac. Most metal elements are higher in the Porcopper mining pit tailing than that of Marcopper comparably because the assaying sample of Marcopper comes from the river while the Porcopper was taken directly from the mining pits. Using the assaying results of Porcopper as similar to Marcopper AMD and since the data from AMDs are higher than the river samples, this brings us to conclusion of urgent rehabilitation and amelioration of the Tapian and San Antonio Pit to mitigate the continuous water contamination at the Calacan Bay, Mogpog and Boac rivers.

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Table 4.0 Comparing Mineral Element Study

	Marcopper ¹	Porcopper ²	Typical Drinking Water
pH	3.08	2.9 -4.9	6.5-8.5
Conductivity	450.00 mS/cm	280-1561 mS/cm	0.20-0.80 mS/cm
Cl ppm (3)	19000 mg/L	-	-
F ppm	2.8 mg/L	-	-
NO3 ppm	<7.0 mg/L	-	-
SO4 ppm	5000 mg/L	-	-
Ag ppb	0.001 mg/L	-	-
Al ppb	210 mg/L	-	-
As ppb	0.030 mg/L	0.153 mg/L	-
Ba ppb	0.004 mg/L	-	-
Ca ppm	1100 mg/L	-	-
Cd ppb	0.030 mg/L	1.2 mg/L	-
Ce ppb	0.076 mg/L	0.13 mg/L	-
Co ppb	0.730 mg/L	2.47 mg/L	-
Cr ppb	<0.100 mg/L	0.04 mg/L	-
Cu ppb	62.000 mg/L	291.1 mg/L	-
Fe ppb	4.800 mg/L	5118.2 mg/L	-
K ppb	410.000 mg/L	-	-
Li ppb	0.270 mg/L	-	-
Mg ppm	1600 mg/L	-	-
Mn ppb	12.000 mg/L	69.8 mg/L	-
Mo ppb	0.005 mg/L	0.015 mg/L	-
Na ppm	11000 mg/L	-	-
Ni ppb	0.460 mg/L	1.48 mg/L	-
P ppb	0.500 mg/L	-	-
Pb ppb	<0.005 mg/L	-	-
Rb ppb	0.020 mg/L	-	-
Sb ppb	<0.002 mg/L	-	-
Se ppb	0.100 mg/L	-	-
SiO2 ppm	<50 mg/L	95.2 mg/L	-
Sr ppb	7.100 mg/L	-	-
U ppb	0.004 mg/L	-	-
V ppb	<0.010 mg/L	0.606 mg/L	-
Zn ppb	2.300 mg/L	692.7 mg/L	-

1 Boac Water River

2 Valea Sesei AMD

3 ppm = [mg/L x 1000 x 24.5] / Molecular Weight

It should be noted that the water sample taken from the Boac river and Valea Sensei AMD does not conform the standard human drinkable water. Deep well water source chemical analysis should be take from around the towns of Boac and Mogpog prior to human consumption.

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3.0 Dolomite¹⁸

Dolomite is an abundant rock-forming mineral in the Philippines whose chemical composition is calcium magnesium carbonate [$\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$]. It is a calcium magnesium carbonate of primarily sedimentary rock dolostone or the igneous rock dolomite marble that has undergone change by pressure and heat. Another rock formation, such as limestone contains dolomite is referred to as a dolomitic limestone.

Dolostone as a rock has number of uses due to its large number of deposits while its aggregate dolomite has very few uses. Crushed dolostone rock is use as an aggregate in concrete, asphalt, railroad ballast, rip-rap, or fill. It is use as an oxidizing agent (calcine) in the cement process. As a mineral, dolomite is used in the production of magnesia (MgO), as an added substance to livestock feed, a oxidizing agent and flux in metal processing, and as an aggregate in the manufacturing ceramics, bricks, and glass.

Dolomite is used in acid neutralization in the chemical processes and manufacturing, it is use in river and soil remediation projects. Although, dolomite has weak reaction to cold dilute hydrochloric acid it reacts in warm hydrochloric acid. In powder form dolomite reacts stronger to hydrochloric acid.

Dolomite as a mineral rock, hosts many iron deposits such as lead, zinc and copper deposits. Iron deposits are formed when high temperature, hydrothermal acid solutions from the earth's crust move upward through a void of the earth's fracture system

¹⁸ Reference [4]

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encounters a dolomitic rock void. The hot acidic solutions then reacts with the dolomite, which results to an increase in pH value causing separation of the hot acidic liquid solution to solid elements of mineral metals.

Dolomite rock serves containment of oil and gas. Calcite is a component of limestone, when converted to dolomite, density increases resulting to the reduction of volume, creating pocket of spaces in the rock that are filled with oil or natural gas thru metamorphosis. Shown in Picture 10 the Philippine Mining Service Corporation (PMSC), extract and processes dolomite at the Alcoy mine on Cebu Island in the Philippines. This product has marginal impurities and is chemically stable.

Picture 10 Cebu Dolomite

PMSC sells dolomite as steelmaking raw material product to steel manufacturers in Japan and Southeast Asia. PMSC sells also dolomite to glass manufacturers and fertilizer manufacturers.

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Table 5.0 Chemical Contents of Dolomite

	MgO	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃
Cebu Dolomite	≥17.5%	34.0±1.0%	≤0.5%	≤0.2%	≤0.15%

The dolomite mined in Alcoy, Cebu contains mainly of magnesium and calcium oxides as shown in Table 5.0

3.1 Literature Review on Dolomite Neutralization of AMD ¹⁹

Before being discharged into a river, AMD should be processed to increase pH and remove heavy metals. Treatment consists of adding strong base chemicals, such as magnesium hydroxide (MgOH), caustic soda (NaOH, sodium hydroxide), soda ash (Na₂CO₃, sodium carbonate), or lime (CaO, calcium oxide, or Ca(OH)₂, calcium dihydroxide). Our study are alkali bases of dolomite, magnesium hydroxide (MgOH) and lime (CaO, calcium oxide, or Ca(OH)₂.

When dolomite [CaMg(CO₃)₂ = MgCO₃ + CaCO₃] reacts to sulfuric acid [H₂SO₄] it produce by-products of Magnesium and Calcium Sulfates and are neutral when dissolve in water Refer to Equation 5. Magnesium sulfate MgSO₄ is a neutral ionic salt. Magnesium sulfate is use in producing medicine. It does not have an acid or a base. Calsium Sulfate is a base chemical material. MgO and CaO being contained in dolomite (Refer to Table 5.0) is potentially best neutralizer for sulfuric acid wastewater.

¹⁹ Ibid 18

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[Acid dissociates when dissolved in water forming H⁺ ions. Base dissociates to OH⁻ ions when dissolved in water. We can identify base chemical solution if it has a oxide or a hydroxide for example MgO or Ca(OH)₂].

4.0 KR100847444B1 Method for Neutralizing AMD Sulfuric Acid Wastewater by Using Calcined Dolomite²⁰

In general alkaline agents such as slake lime (quick lime) (Ca (OH) ₂), magnesium hydroxide, caustic soda and sodium carbonate are used as a neutralizing agent for sulfuric acid in wastewater treatment. There are two purposes of these patent application which is approved. One, is to reduce the cost of the neutralization of sulfuric acid in wastewater treatment process. Two, to reduce the amount of sludge generated using the generally used neutralizing agents. The method is to use light calcine dolomite as an alternative to neutralize sulfuric acid. The process was performed in an experimental quantity to compare dolomite performance in neutralizing sulfuric acid with other alkali agents.

4.1 Methodology

The patent invention is a method for neutralizing sulfuric acid in wastewater using light calcinal dolomite. The light calcined dolomite (CaMgCO₃) is heated at 800 ~ 1,000 °C 40-80 hours to vaporize the CO₂ component of the dolomite and improve the remaining main component CaO and MgO by least 85.0% by weight. The resulting material improves alkalinity of a raw mined dolomite [CaMg(CO₃)₂ = MgCO₃ + CaCO₃]

²⁰ Reference 5

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(at least 90% alkalinity), so that it can be efficiently neutralize sulfuric acid wastewater with small amount of light calcined dolomite input. The Cebu dolomite characteristic is shown in Table 5.0.

The use of Cebu mined dolomite is preferable in our country because of its abundance and cost only between Php 600 to Php 1,000 per ton. Raw dolomite contains 52% CaO and MgO and is 33% by weight less than the light calcined dolomite (refer to Table 5.0). Industry practice calls for the use of alkali agents such as slaked lime (quick lime) ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), magnesium hydroxide, caustic soda and sodium carbonate, as neutralizing agent for sulfuric acid. "The commonly use of slaked lime (quick lime) to neutralize sulfuric acid wastewater (pH 7.0 ~ 11.0) generates gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), an insoluble substance (sludge), during the neutralization reaction. Quick lime has a very low in solubility (0.22 g / 100 g water) and produces sludge in large quantities, which dramatically increases the cost of wastewater treatment. The weight required to neutralize 1.0 ton of sulfuric acid in the calcined circuit is 1.4 tons of gypsum formed through chemical reaction. The by-product gypsum needs to be treated with water as require as post-treatment"²¹.

The patent would be able to prove its viability by conducting comparative laboratory experiments comparing dolomite with other alkali agents such as the commonly used slake lime and magnesium hydroxide for neutralizing sulfuric acid. The comparative data would be the resulting acidity of the by-product in pH value based on the amount of sulfuric acid dosage.

²¹ Ibid 20

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4.1.1 Experimental Procedure of KR100847444B1 Method

4.1.1.1 Apparatus

Abstract²² (Corrected)

“The method for neutralizing sulfuric acid wastewater by using calcined dolomite through an apparatus (Shown in Figure 1.0). The neutralization process of sulfuric acid wastewater starts with an Equalization Tank (12) on which sulfuric acid waste is injected and mixed thru an air blower(10). From (12) the sulfuric acid wastewater is transferred thru pipe (P1) by the operation of a Transfer Pump (13) to the First Settling Tank (20) to which dolomite is introduced to mix with sulfuric acid waterwaste. The reaction betweenf dolomite and sulfuric acid wastewater resulted gypsum sludge residue. The first stage treatment of the sulfuric acid wastewater increased the pH-value of the wastewater and is transferred thru pipe (P2) to the First Settling Tank (20), The gypsum sludge is settled in (20) and is transferred Gypsum Settling Tank (19). The first stage treated wastewater mixture with a higher pH-value is transferred thru pipe (P3) to a Second Reaction Tank (22) where a second dolomite is introduced resulting to a much higher pH-value of the treated wastewater and is transferred to a Second Settling Tank (24) through pipe (P4). At (24) gypsum sludge settled on a bottom of (24). From tank (24), the second treated water discharges to pipe (P5) while the gypsum sludge is transferred to (19). From (19) the gypsum sludge is dehydrated thru a Dehydrator(14) for dehydrating the gypsum to separate waste gypsum and dolomite and transfer dolomite filtrate to the first reaction tank. A dehydrator (14) generates

²² Ibid 22

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waste gypsum from (19) is disposed of by waste treatment, and the recovered dolomite filtrate is transferred to the First Reactor (16). This method comprises: injecting calcined dolomite into the first and second reaction tanks to neutralize the sulfuric acid wastewater, neutralizing sulfuric acid wastewater with the calcined dolomite to a pH range of 1.5 to 11.0 in the first reaction tank; and neutralizing the sulfuric acid wastewater again with the calcined dolomite to a pH range of 7.5 to 11.0 to perform an efficient reaction of high concentration fluorine in the second reaction tank”.

Figure 1.0 Apparatus Schematic Process Diagram

4.1.1.2 Procedure

To achieve a two-stage process for the above procedural objective, a blower is installed for the equalization or mixing of sulfuric acid wastewater in Tank 12. Thru the

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transfer pump 13 the equalized or mixed sulfuric acid is transferred to the first Reaction Tank 16 through the pipe P1.

In the first Reaction Tank dolomite is introduced in which the mixture reacted in the first reactor (16). The mixture is transported through the pipe P2 to settle the gypsum in the Gypsum Settling Tank (19) thru the First Settling Tank (20). The first treatment water from (20), excluding for the gypsum settled in the first settling tank 20, is transferred through the pipe (P3) to the Second Reaction Tank (22). Dolomite is transferred to (22). The second stage treatment wastewater is route to the Second Settling Tank (24) thru pipe P4. Except for the gypsum at (24), the second treated wastewater is transferred through the pipe P5 and discharged. The gypsum in (24) is settled on the bottom surface of (24) and finally discharged to (19) to be dehydrated as waste gypsum. Recovered dolomite filtrate from a dehydrator (14) will be transferred to a Reaction Tank (16). And the materials introduced into the (22) are respectively light dolomite after neutralizing the sulfuric acid wastewater to pH 1.5 to 11.0 in the first reactor (16) and to achieve a higher pH 7.5 and higher thru reactor (22).

4.1.2 Literature Review Chemistry

To achieve the two purposes of this patent, aside from that dolomite is a potentially effective in increasing the pH-value sulfuric wastewater, is first to reduce cost of neutralization and second to show the solubility of the by-products of neutralization of sulfuric wastewater using dolomite is higher.

The light dolomite used in this invention is calcined dolomite (CaMgCO_3) treated at 800 ~ 1,000 °C 40-80 hours to vaporize the CO_2 component of the dolomite and blow off

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the remaining main component CaO and MgO at least 85.0% by weight. It is made of a material that improves alkalinity by at least 90%, so that it can be efficiently neutralized with a small amount of dolomite input.

The Cebu dolomite contains 17.5% MgO and 34.0% CaO. This was found to be significantly higher alkalinity compared to the alkalinity of hydrated lime (quick lime). The Cebu dolomite is use as raw material product to steel manufacturers in Japan and Southeast Asia, and is also use in glass manufacturing and fertilizer production.

If you look at the chemical equation below using Cebu dolomite,

[Cebu Dolomite mixed with sulfuric acid wastewater]

The MgO component contained in the small dolomite reacts with sulfuric acid to form a salt called magnesium sulfate ($\text{MgSO}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), which has a high solubility at room temperature and almost dissolved in water. Since it does not form insoluble materials such as CaSO_4 (which is relatively low in solubility), sludge generation can be reduced to an equivalent amount of MgO present in dolomite.

In this patent, light dolomite is used instead of Cebu dolomite , resulting in a 50% reduction in sludge using dolomite compared with hydrated lime in the following chemical reaction.

[Light Dolomite vaporized CO_2 reacted with sulfuric acid wastewater]

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Magnesium Sulfate (MgSO_4), generated in the reaction (Equation 8), is present in the dissolved state of water [$\text{MgSO}_4 + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$] and does not generate sludge and avoid an added treatment cost in processing sludge residue. This greatly reduces the operation of dehydrators and waste landfill costs. The use of light dolomite can therefore significantly reduce insoluble solids when used in sulfuric acid wastewater and sulfuric acid complex wastewater. Calcium Sulfate is less soluble than Magnesium Sulfate.

For comparison purposes, below is the chemical composition of both Light Dolomite and the Cebu Dolomite by weight and is as follows:

Table 6.0 Comparing Cebu Dolomite and Light Dolomite

Description	MgO	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃
Cebu Dolomite	≥17.5%	34.0±1.0%	≤0.5%	≤0.2%	≤0.15%
KR100847444B1 Light Dolomite	30-40%	50-60%	1.2- 1.5%	0.1- 1%	0.1-1%

4.2 KR100847444B1 Method Results

To evaluate the performance and effectivity of dolomite in neutralizing sulfuric acid in mine tailings, the data of patent KR100847444B1 study will be used to determine the effectivity compared other alkali based neutralizing agent.

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Table 7.0. Comparative Additive Dosage pH-Value of Alkali and Sulfuric Acid Mixture-1

Dosage (ppm)	pH		
	Dolomite*	30% slaked lime	35% magnesium hydroxide
0.000	1.00	1.00	1.00
4,000	1.10	1.07	1.02
2,000	1.15	1.10	1.07
2,000	1.25	1.12	1.00
2,000	1.25	1.14	1.10
2,000	1.40	1.23	1.19
2,000	1.70	1.37	1.27
2,000	2.25	1.55	1.41
2,000	8.47	1.87	1.59
2,000		8.79	1.60
2,000			1.83
2,000			2.19
2,000			7.20
Total input amount (ppm)	Kazol 1025	30% slaked lime	35% magnesium hydroxide
	18,000	20,000	26,000
Compared to Dolomite (%)	100%	111%	144%

*Kazol 1025

In Table 6 is a comparative pH-values between dolomite, slake lime and magnesium hydroxide. At accumulative amount of dolomite in parts per million (ppm) of 18,000 ppm dolomite was able to reach a pH-value of 8.47 while slake lime and magnesium hydroxide reach 20,000 ppm at 8.79 pH-value and 26,000 ppm at 7.20 pH-value respectively. Similarly, in Table 7 with the addition of Sodium Carbonate and Caustic resulted to the same results where dolomite is more efficient in neutralizing sulfuric acid at the least amount required therefore cheaper and resulting to more less insoluble to water.

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Table 8. Tabulated Cumulative Dosage pH-Value of Alkali and Sulfuric Acid Mixture-2

Dosage (ppm)	pH					
	Dolomite* Kazol 1025	30% slaked lime	35% magnesium hydroxide	15% Sodium Carbonate	25% Caustic Soda	
0,000	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	
4,000	1.10	1.07	1.02	1.02	1.14	
6,000	1.15	1.10	1.07	1.02	1.17	
8,000	1.25	1.12	1.09	1.06	1.20	
10,000	1.40	1.14	1.10	1.09	1.32	
12,000	1.70	1.23	1.19	1.10	1.71	
14,000	2.25	1.37	1.27	1.23	2.31	
16,000	8.47	1.55	1.41	1.32	3.21	
18,000		1.87	1.59	1.43	8.78	
20,000		8.79	1.60	1.46		
22,000			1.83	1.48		
24,000			2.19	1.51		
26,000			7.20	1.52		
28,000				1.54		
36,000				1.65		
44,000				1.80		
52,000				2.06		
60,000				2.64		
68,000				5.38		
72,000				5.79		
76,000				6.04		
80,000				6.24		
Dosage (ppm)	pH					
	Dolomite* Kazol 1025	30% slaked lime	35% magnesium hydroxide	15% Sodium Carbonate	25% Caustic Soda	
84,000				6.42		
88,000				6.58		
102,000				6.94		
106,000				7.15		
110,000				7.47		
114,000				8.04		
Total input amount (ppm)		CaMg(CO ₃) ₂	30% Ca (OH) ₂	35% Mg (OH) ₂	15% Na ₂ CO ₃	25% NaOH
		16,000	20,000	26,000	114,000	18,000
Compared to Dolomite (%)		100%	125%	162%	712%	112%

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Based on Table 7 and Table 8 generated by the study of the approved Patent Application filed by 우정남, 이윤남 in 2008-07-21 would clearly show that light calcine dolomite has the less dosage and amount to achieve a pH value of 8.7 when reacted with sulfuric acid waste. This indicates the effectiveness of dolomite to prevent sulfuric acid AMD from contaminating the Boac and Mogpog river when it replaces the existing AMD liquid pond in the Tapian and San Antonio pit. The by-product between the reaction of dolomite and AMD sulfuric acid are neutral chemicals (Equation 5, 7 and 8) that will not dangerously compromise the quality of the river waters of Boac and Mopog.

5.0 Concept of Remediation : A Case Study of Dolomite in South Africa's West Rand Gold Field

The approved patent Application filed by 우정남, 이윤남 in 2008-07-21 under KR100847444B1 Method provide us with a conclusive insight that dolomite is an effective neutralizer of sulfuric waterwaste. Dolomite when reacting to sulfuric acid produces magnesium sulfate that is soluble to water but produces calcium sulfate that is insoluble.

Our remediation concept of filling-up the open-pit containing AMD with dolomite as shown in figure below is a model similar to the case of the Westland Rand Goldfield of Witwatersrand. The case is where the streams and subsurface water flow is adjacent to a dolomite aquifer that protects it from the gold mine AMD discharge. Test where conducted to find a conclusion of the possibility of the dissolution of the dolomite aquifer that would result to the contamination of the streams and subsurface.

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Figure 2.0 Schematic Cross-Section of Marcopper Open Pit

5.1 The Abstract ²³

“West Rand Goldfield of the Witwatersrand discharge AMD since 2002 into river streams and its subsurface into the near-by dolomitic aquifer. It was observed that the subsurface discharge has recharge the dolomitic aquifer. This raised the alarm of the possibility of the decomposition of dolomite that might accelerate to gradual settling in a particular land area. However, in laboratory test conducted it was evident that the formation carbonates on the aquifer surfaces serves as a f resistant mineral coatings thus, limit the preventing decomposition and natural deterioration of dolomite”.

²³ Reference [8]

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5.2 Introduction²⁴

“West Rand Gold Field in South Africa has been mining gold at the start of the 19th century. The gold is located in an aggregate sections within an Achaean volcano – sedimentary basin, overlapped by dolomites of the Proterozoic Transvaal Supergroup (Toens and Griffiths 1964). The mineralized aggregates contains some amounts of pyrite, causing the creation of acid mine drainage (AMD) when expose to water and air by the mining process (Coetzee et al 2005). Fig.1 shows the spatial location of the West Central and East Rand Gold Fields vis-à-vis to the Out Crop of the Malmani Dolomite. Authorities are worried of the possibility of AMD generated in Witwatersrand contaminate the underground water resources located within the dolomite aquifer. It should be noted Hobbs and Cobbing (2007)²⁵ and while Krige (2006) proposes that acidic water entering dolomite and the information of sinkholes. Krige (2006)²⁶ study identifies the possibility of iron and sulphate rich precipitates forming in the reactions between dolomite and both AMD containing sulfuric acid and uses results derived from consideration of the reaction which HCl, as would be used in an acid base accounting for Sobek test (Sobek et al. 1978). To determine the potential dissolution of dolomite, the study aims to determine the extent of the effect of the AMD from Witwatersrand entering the groundwater in an adjacent dolomitic areas.”

²⁴ Ibid 23 Sentences are slightly restructured

²⁵ Reference [8]

²⁶ Reference [9]

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Fig. 1 Location of the West, Central and East Rand Goldfields relative to the City of Johannesburg and surrounding urban areas and the outcrop of the Malmani Dolomite (Ramontja et al. 2011).

Figure 3.0 Mine Site of the West Central & East Rand Goldfields

5.3 Case Experiments²⁷

When West Rand Goldfield started to discharge AMD in 2002 there was a concern that the dolomite field surrounding the water source of Johannesburg would react to the AMD discharges of the West Rand Gold Mining and possibly contaminate the water source. There were four (4) experiments conducted with the objective of determining the performance of dolomite in preventing the contamination by AMD of the adjacent groundwater aquifer.

5.3.1 Case 1 Initial Test of Dolomite to Neutralize AMD

Qualitative tests were undertaken to determine the possibility that dolomite can neutralize AMD. The methodology is rather simple. Dolomite chips were mixed and shaken overnight to an AMD taken from the West Rand. It is observed that the pH-value slightly increased while orange precipitate was found at the surface of the dolomite. Observations showed mineral iron in AMD was precipitating to “hydroxide mineral:

²⁷ Ibid 24

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[(Fe(OH)₃ –Equation 3 and 4] and armoring (coating) the dolomite surface preventing neutralization from taking place”²⁸.

Fig. 2 Photomicrographs (PPL) of dolomite before (a) and after (b) leaching with AMD collected the West Rand Gold Field (the dark line in the images is a line scribed in the polished thin section to allow the identification of the same area before and after leaching).

Picture 11.0

Shown above in Picture 11.0 is a photomicrographic picture of dolomite before the reaction with AMD and after the reaction. The size seems did not change indication a minimal reaction between dolomite and AMD. Possibly cause by (Fe(OH)₃ coating of dolomite.

5.3.2 Case 2 Petrographic Mineralogical Investigation and Study

Slices of dolomite were polished then dipped to AMD from a shaft that H₂O decants²⁹ at Randfontein Estates Goldmine. The thin pieces of dolomites are placed in breakers (cylindrical containers with flat bottoms and a small spout) and where filled with AMD taken from the mining shafts and sealed to avoid oxygen from entering the beaker. These are then agitated slowly for one week to allow steady mix-flow of AMD thru the dolomite

²⁸ Ibid 27

²⁹ Decants are liquids separated from solid by removing the liquid layer at the top of the the layer of solid.

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sample. The dolomite pieces were air dried to determine the effects of AMD immersion.

The results are shown in Table 9.0.

Table 9.0 Chemical Parameters of AMD before and after leaching of dolomite thin sections³⁰.

Sample	pH Initial	Salinity Electrical Conductivity Before (ppm)	Oxidation Reduction Potential (ORP)– Before (mV)	pH- Post Leaching	Salinity Electrical Conductivity After leaching (mS/m)	Oxidation Reduction Potential ORP After Leaching(mV)
Dolomite (a)	5.44	3014	-57	4.405	2827	113
Dolomite (b)	5.44	3014	-57	4.312	2805	110
Blank (a)	5.44	3014	-57	4.498	2843	85
Blank (b)	5.44	3014	-57	3.898	3069	119

Table 9.0 would indicate a drop in pH-value and salinity but increase in ORP due to oxidation of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} with associated lowering of pH-value. It also indicated a precipitation of Fe^{3+} hydroxide as shown in Equations 2,3 and 4 and Picture 11.0. No neutralization has been observed due to the small amount of dolomite sample.

However, petrographic and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) identified the precipitates in the sample to be largely gypsum ($CaSO_4$) Equation 8 and goetite ($FeO(OH)$) Equation 2, 3 and 4 and Picture 12.0. This indicates neutralization took place as shown in Picture 12.0 the gypsum precipitates in accordance with Equation 8.

³⁰ Ibid 28

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Fig. 3 Typical SEM image of the precipitate phases in the leached dolomite samples

Picture 12.0 Typical SEM Image of the Precipitate Phases

5.3.3 Column Test using Synthetic AMD

This test that resulted in Table 10.0 was to replicate AMD flow through a dolomite rock formation. This test is also a simulation of the model we proposed shown in Figure 2.0. Dolomite was placed in a column test glass tube then poured synthetic AMD to replicate the flow through a dolomitic rock formation. A synthetic AMD was used in this test and is aimed to approximate the AMD of East Rand Goldfield, in such a way to limit the iron solution, to prevent rapid armoring of dolomites by other ferrous metal mineral.

Fig. 4 Precipitate forming at the bottom of a column due to the reaction between synthetic AMD and dolomite.

Fig. 5 SEM image of the amorphous and crystalline precipitate generated in the reaction between synthetic AMD and dolomite.

Picture 13.0 SEM Image

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AMD was constantly flowed into vertical glass columns that contains various sizes of dolomite at a rate of about 0.012 gallons/lb/day. The 5 months test includes the recording of pH, EC and chemical analysis of leachates. The results are summarized in Table 10.0

[1] Attenuation means decrease concentration

Chemical Specimen	Input Solution Range	Column Leachate Range	Comments
AMD pH	3.6	7.5-8.5	<u>Dolomite showed its efficaciousness in neutralizing synthetic AMD solution during the time of the experiment</u>
Fe	1.5-13 ppm	<0.05 ppm	<u>Iron was dissolved into insoluble solid during the experiment period</u>
Al	16-21 ppm	<0.025-0.5 ppm	<u>Aluminums was strongly reduced during the chemical reactions with dolomite</u>
SO ₄	730-920 ppm	630-920 ppm	<u>Sulphate was hardly reduced during the chemical reactions with dolomite.</u>
Ca	8-21 ppm	60-100 ppm	<u>Calcium was reduced to carbonates when mixed with dolomite during the laboratory test.</u>
Mg	65-77	94-131 ppm	<u>Some magnesium was converted to a solution.</u>

Table 10.0 Column Test Results for Synthetic AMD³¹

During the five-month test that resulted to Table 10.0, a white and orange colored precipitate mineral formed at the bottom of the columns shown Picture 13.0. A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) investigation using energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS),

³¹ Ibid 30

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shows a crystalline and amorphous (botryoidal) mineral containing Al, O and S Picture 13 (Fig. 5)

The test showed that dolomite can neutralize AMD. The result showed, that sufficient iron content should be added to synthetic AMD. It was suggested to use laboratory generated AMD using pyrite rock (sulfuric ferrous) material with O₂ and H₂O to make a more rational conclusion.

5.3.4 Column Glass Test Using Laboratory Produced AMD

To make a more rational results in a laboratory test between the reaction of dolomite and AMD of the West Rand Gold Field another test with the same procedure as in paragraph 5.1.3 was conducted by replacing the synthetic AMD solution with leachate produced in the laboratory where Witwatersrand ore is mixed to water and oxygen resulting to an acidic solution, as shown in Equation 1 and redox reaction in Equation 2,3,and 4. This procedure resulted to a leachate containing iron concentration of 20-200 ppm which is similar to the figures of West Rand. The result of this test indicates that effectiveness of dolomite to neutralize AMD. In Picture 14.0 red iron rich precipitate formed rapidly and is similar to the precipitates seen on-site when AMD is exposed to dolomitic material on the surface.

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Fig. 6 Iron-rich precipitate in a dolomite-filled column fed with lab-generated AMD

Picture 14.0

5.3.5 Conclusions on the Above Experiments³²

Laboratory tests was conducted to evaluate the effect of AMD produced from the West Rand Gold Field of migrating into dolomitic aquifers. The test also will evaluate the generated precipitates when AMD reacts dolomite surfaces that will coats (armour) the dolomite to prevent more reactions from happening. This reaction between dolomite and AMD mitigates the risk of sinkhole formation. The reaction would stop the migration of AMD thru the dolomite aquifer and groundwater. This would also weaken the reaction of AMD using dolomitic material.

Caution: The laboratory investigation is limited to the concepts of a geochemical model. The test was undertaken to give significance to realistic laboratory simulations of environmental systems. Test methods centered on the potential of AMD to cover the pyrite rock surfaces with precipitates but has to take note of the risk of forming sinkhole and the potential of dolomite to neutralize AMD.

³² Ibid 31

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Taking field samples of AMD to assess the values of pH and chemical reduction-oxidation conditions it was needed to evaluate the chemical reactions which are pH are not similar in the affected area. There is a need for a good assessment of the local hydrogeology. Taking rock samples and precipitates helps assess the chemical reactions that occurred in the mine site.

5.3.6 Observation on the Experiment

The Column test (5.1.4) is a promising methodology of experimenting the performance of the reaction between dolomite and AMD. Since the experiment was performed in a column which is presumed to be contained, the products or precipitates of the reaction are not quantified in terms of the amount or percentage of the precipitates that was dissolved in liquid and the the amount of precipitates that remains as undissolved compound. In Equation 7

The reaction between dolomite [$\text{MgCO}_3 + \text{CaCO}_3$] and AMD [$2\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$] results to [MgSO_4] magnesium sulfate that completely dissolves in liquid and calcium sulfate [CaSO_4] that does not dissolve in liquid but remains as a precipitate.

Since metal and acid reacts in redox the reddish iron oxide-hydroxide precipitate is produced mixed with calcium sulfate (gypsum) as shown in the following chemical equations:

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The simultaneous redox between metal and acid results to a reddish ferrous hydroxide $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ precipitate that mixed with calcium sulfate (gypsum) as shown in Picture 14. Since magnesium sulfate dissolves into liquid the amount of dolomite will be reduced during the reaction period. This is the concern about the formation of sinkhole when dolomite reacts into magnesium sulfate that dissolve to liquid and migrates to the groundwater creating an empty crevice in the dolomite aquifer.

6.1 Background

In Chapter 10 Remediation and Clean-up Options provided by the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in their book titled "Abandoned Mine Sites Characterization and Clean-Up Handbook" provided a basic types and available technologies for mining and mineral processing sites remediation.

Listed below are conventional technologies that can be adapted for the Collection, Diversion, and Containment in the mine sites treatment where technologies are not able control the contaminants to an acceptable level. These engineering systems can reduce or minimize the release of contained contaminants to the natural environment. These are 10 engineering methods used today and listed in the EPA handbook, namely:

1. Landfill Disposal
2. Cut-off Walls (slurry walls, cement walls and sheet piles)
3. Pumping Ground Water
4. Capping
5. Detention and Treatment

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6. Settling Basin
7. Erosion Controls (capping, wind breaks and diversion)
8. Interceptor Trenches
9. Diversion (run-on controls, capping)
10. Stream Channel Erosion Control

In this study we are using all of the 10 technologies recommended by the EPA Manual as shown in Figure 4.0 and Picture 15.0 below:

Figure 4.0 Reverse Osmosis Process

This study was centered on items 1, 2, 3, 5 and 6 as discussed below:

1.0 Land Fill by using dolomite as the protective material barrier between AMD and the water resource of Boac river and Mogpog river. This is a similar situation of the West Rand Gold Field where a mass of dolomite field serves to protect the underground water resource of Johannesburg from AMD.

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2.0 Cut-off Walls are exposed ferrous sulfide rock walls that are covered with cemented walls to avoid exposure to water and air and prevent the formation of sulfuric acid or AMD.

3.0 Pumping AMD Water for processing to a water resource that can be use as a non-potable resource for domestic use or in agriculture. The AMD will be stored in a tank thru a pump then from the tank AMD will be processed thru reverse osmosis.

4.0 From the reverse osmosis process, it will be stored in water tanks for chemical monitoring to meet the non-potable water chemical standards.

Figure 1.3 Tapian ore-body (open pit) in Marinduque in 2002
(Photo: Catherine Coumans/Mining Watch Canada)

Picture 15.0 Tapian ore-body (Open Pit) in Marinduque in 2002

6.2 Reverse Osmosis Process

For engineer's filtration always means that the filter is located on the intake side of the pump or the less pressure side of the pump. Reverse osmosis is the opposite or the reverse side of a pump where filters are located at the pump outlet or the high-pressure side. The US Environment Protection Agency (EPA) refers to reverse osmosis as:

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“The pressure-driven separation of contaminants through a semi-permeable membrane that allows water to pass through while retaining contaminants. The dissolved ions are retained in a concentrated brine solution that requires management or disposal (Figure 15.0). Reverse osmosis is a proven method to demineralize acid mine drainage (AMD) . However, it does require significant construction and operating costs”³³.

Figure 11: Diagram of Simplified Reverse Osmosis Technology

Figure 5.0 Reverse Osmosis

“Reverse osmosis involves a semipermeable membrane through which almost pure water is removed from a concentrated input solution by applying pressure, leaving a more highly concentrated brine solution. The membrane is the primary component of a reverse osmosis system. Durable membranes resistant to chemical and microbial agents that retain structural stability over long operating periods are essential. Pre-treatment is necessary to prevent membrane fouling, particularly if the water contains elevated levels of hardness (i.e., calcium or magnesium) or total suspended solids. With pre-treatment and routine maintenance, membranes typically last two to five years”³⁴.

³³ Reference 10

³⁴ Ibid 33

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“The brine produced is typically 20 to 30 percent of the influent flow in a single system, depending on influent water quality. The process produces a concentrated waste stream that must be disposed of properly. Various disposal options are available. However, the concentrated waste stream is typically disposed of through evaporation, deep well injection or ocean discharge”³⁵.

7.0 Conclusion

The ineffective conventional impoundment methods used by Marcopper consist of the using the unused mine pit with a depth of 300 meter that created 425 pounds per square inch head pressure when filled with AMD. Embankments for containments located downstream of the mine tailing discharge where not sufficient and mine tailings water are accumulated and discharged as a sub-marine disposal mechanism into Calacan Bay. In another situation, solid mine tailings are used as filling material for the unused mining pit failed resulting to massive environmental disaster. Tight execution of legislation failed, and public awareness failed to check the soil stability of embankments and dams, and neglect to monitor the disposal of mine tailings by government agencies. The dam failure resulted to the discharge of large volume of mine tailing waste resulting to a socio-environmental disaster and medial issues to the people of Marinduque.

The abandoned mines is a major on environmental and human health issue that requires the mitigation of AMD by neutralizing acid and diverting the rainwater runoff to prevent water from entering the mine tailing pit; and managing the disposal of mine tailings in case reverse osmosis process³⁶ is used.

³⁵ Ibid 34

³⁶ Reference 11

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Dolomite will serve as a protective barrier against AMD from permeating into the Boac and Mogpog river. The study showed that dolomite neutralize sulfuric acid waste based on two studies one being of commercial interest as an alternative to the traditional efficient way of acid neutralization such as using lime. The other as dolomite field serving as a barrier for underground water resource in preventing AMD from permeating into the water resource.

AMD present at the Tapian and San Antonio copper mine pit will continue to flow into the Boac and Mogpog rivers. The reason for this is continuous exposure of pyrite sulfide rocks to rainwater and air. Unless mitigated by layering and sealing the pyrite rock surface by cement and provide drainage run-down trench that would lead to a containment tank for processing thru reverse osmosis, AMD will continue to be a threat to the community. This study has presented a solution that needs to be further developed into a working model by conducting prototype models in a small scale prior to investing for a large-scale full-blown operation. The process is simple, and the equipment's are commercially available.

Aside from addressing the neutralization of AMD on abandoned Marcopper mines the process of forest succession thru amelioration should be started as early as possible. In

Appendix 1.0 we presented the concept processes for a forest succession.

In **Appendix 2.0** is an estimated volume of dolomite needed to remediate the abandoned Tapian and San Antonio mining pit. An estimated number of 14 ton dump truck is 300 dump trucks or 600-7 ton dump trucks for the Tapian mining pit and similarly 300 -14 ton dump trucks or 600 – 7 ton dump truck for the San Antonio mine pit.

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Appendix I Forest Succession

[For Information Only]

1. Reforestration Planning and Implementation

1.1 Principle:

After mining (copper), the forest ecological process that was disrupted must be brought back to its primary role and composition by allowing forest succession activity. Forest succession is an innate activity of trees and shrubs to recover its own habitat after a disruption of its innate activity through a lengthy activity of tree and shrub substitution and terrestrial improvement.

The earlier forest of Mount Tapian consist of narra, molave, Philippine mahogany and dipterocarp trees should not be reinstated immediately. Instead, colonial type of trees and shrubs, such as seed-bearing trees, shrubs, and timber woods that can sustain itself in acidic soil, infertile soil, hot, and humid climate will be the first to sustain its growth. These colonial trees and shrubs will be overwhelmed by ecologically adaptable timber woods after ages.

After

Before

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Picture A1.0

Amelioration will assist growth of trees by soil conditioning using nitrogen and organic matter. Eventually insect and animal habitat is created that would assist growth of timber wood species. If forest restoration is left to nature without human intervention natural forest succession would require several hundred years for the hardwoods to dominate. (Picture A1.0)

1.2 Method

The reforestation procedures proposed below (Figure 1.0) would hasten the growth of trees and shrubs and at the same time secure terrestrial stability and prevent soil degradation that could result to massive landslides. At the same time growth of grasses and seed bearing plants, shrubs and trees are secured.

Figure 1.0

Ideally, trees and shrubs complements a particular task, and supplements these tasks to other trees and shrubs. The reforested, tree-complementary grasses immediately stabilize the top soil of mine site. (Figure 2.0). *Sods (grass) are implanted on acid rock drain*

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(ARD) to prevent oxygen from interacting with the sulfide waste rocks. When sulfide rocks interact with air and rainwater sulfuric acid is produced. Turf then given-way to seed bearing tress and shrub when nitrogen in the soil becomes limited for turf-growth. The seed bearing shrubs takes time to grow and will take a while to mature until the seed-bearing trees is full grown. However, seed bearing shrub provide nutrients to the soil until the seed-bearing trees is full grown to provide shelter to the seed-bearing shrubs. In principle, seed-bearing trees and shrubs provide nutrients to the soil at its early stages of its growth until the seed-bearing trees fully matured to provide cover shelter to the seed-bearing shrubs. It is therefore important to seek the proper combination of seed-bearing shrubs and tree in a certain mine area in order to establish compatibility This activity of coordinating seed-bearing shrub and with seed-bearing trees growth affinity of each other, is the aim of forest succession. The following steps are recommended:

Figure 2.0

Prepare the land for reforestation. Cultivate the finest top soil for shrub and tree planting, aid the shrubs and trees increase at its anticipated change size, and promote and prioritize planting of endemic seed-bearing shrubs and trees. Then:

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- Replace mine soils with topsoil available in an undisturbed portion of the mines that are endemic or a replacement suitable for shrubs and trees. Dig at least 3 feet wide square and at least 4 feet deep for soil replacement with endemic or suitable soil to . (Figure 3.0)
- Do not compress the soil and keep it loose.
- Cover the new planted shrub or tree to prevent erosion and apply fertilizer that is low in nitrogen but in sufficient amount of phosphorus.

Figure 3.0

2. Monitoring and Review

Monitor the water chemical properties of the Mogpog and Boac River to include acidity level, chemical composition and bacteria content. Monitoring would be weekly for six months and monthly in the succeeding monitoring. The sample should be taken ever 500 meter.

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Appendix 2.0 Estimated Volume of Dolomite Needed To Remediate The Tapian and San Antonio Abandoned Mine Pit

Below is my way of estimating the amount in volume of dolomite that could be need to remediate the Tapian and San Antonio mining open pit.

A. Tapian Pit

Picture 1.0 Tapian Mining Pit

In Picture 1.0 the Area taken of the Tapian Pit from Google Earth is about 543,919 square meters (54 hectares). To get an equivalent estimated volume for an initial study a 20 meter depth to estimate the volume using the formula of the cone as shown below:

$$V = \frac{\pi r^2}{3} h$$

Where R is determined as an equivalent radius of area "A" equal to 543,919 square meters

$$A = \pi R^2$$

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{A}{\pi}}$$

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{544,000}{\pi}}$$

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$$R = 416 \text{ meters}$$

$$r = 22 \text{ meters}$$

$$h = 10 \text{ meters}$$

$$V = \frac{\pi r^2}{3} h$$

$$V = \frac{\pi \times 22^2}{3} 10$$

$$= 5,100 \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{Weight} = \text{Density} \times \text{Volume}$$

$$= 737 \text{ kg / m}^3 \times 5,100 \text{ m}^3 / 1000 \text{ kg / ton}$$

$$= 3,760 \text{ tons}$$

$$= \text{plus } 10 \text{ allowance} = 4,200 \text{ tons}$$

Equivalent to 300 -14 ton dump trucks or 600– 7 ton dump trucks.

Estimated Cost is about Php 1000 per ton plus Php 2,000 transport cost is about Php 13 million.

In Picture 2.0 the Area taken of the San Antonio Pit from Google Earth is about

518,177 square meters (52 hectares). To get an estimated volume for an initial study a

10 meter

depth to estimate the equivalent volume using the formula of the cone as shown

below:

B. San Antonio Pit

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Picture 2.0 San Antonio Mining Pit

$$V = \frac{\pi r^2}{3} h$$

Where R is determined as an equivalent radius of area "A" equal to 518,177 square meters

$$A = \pi R^2$$

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{A}{\pi}}$$

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{518,176}{\pi}}$$

$$R = 406 \text{ meters}$$

$$r = 22 \text{ meters}$$

$$h = 10 \text{ meters}$$

$$V = \frac{\pi r^2}{3} h$$

$$V = \frac{\pi \times 22^2}{3} \times 10$$

$$= 5,100 \text{ m}^3$$

Weight = Density x Volume

$$= 737 \text{ kg / m}^3 \times 5,100 \text{ m}^3 / 1000 \text{ kg / ton}$$

$$= 3,760 \text{ tons}$$

$$= \text{plus } 10\% \text{ allowance} = 4200 \text{ tons}$$

Equivalent to 300 -14 ton dump trucks or 600 – 7 ton dump trucks.

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Estimated Cost is about Php 1000 per ton plus Php 2,000 transport cost is about Php 13 million

Note: The above estimate maybe more or less between a 30% range. The suggested method would be to have a measurement survey of the Taipan and San Antonio pit to get a more accurate volume of dolomite needed to remediate the AMD or attenuated sulfuric acid waste. This values can serve as a cost estimate for budgetary purposes only.

I would suggest an h = 5 meters initially then another 5 meters if needed. Or that would be about 300-14 ton dump truck or 600 -7 ton dump truck.

[Submitted as an instructed additional information of my special study problem “The Study to use Dolomite to Neutralize Sulfuric Acid in the Abandoned Copper Mine Pits in Marinduque”].

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